

Title: Using Deep Learning to predict the mortality of Leukemia patients

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INTRODUCTION:

Personalized medicine is the approach that tailors the treatment of patients based on their unique genetic makeup and genetic environment. When equipped with details of individual variation, physicians can separate patients into subgroups to predict which patients must be treated aggressively and which patients would respond to one drug rather than another. Personalized medicine is now being applied towards the prediction of mortality in childhood Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) patients. This is because individual children differ in the sensitivity of their leukemic cells and in their response to treatment-related toxicity.

Currently, mortality prediction for childhood ALL is based on risk-stratification performed by expert doctors. The genotypic (actual set of genes), phenotypic (expression of those genes in observable traits) and clinical information is used to stratify children into various risk categories. The information collected by doctors for risk-stratification include response to certain drugs, clinical factors such as age and gender and biological measurements such as white blood cell count.

AIM:

The goal is to automate the prediction of childhood ALL mortality using genotypic and phenotypic information of patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The 3 datasets- SNP, Affymetrix and clinical datasets, consist of gene expression data derived from the diagnostic bone marrow of 146 childhood Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) patients. The data was collected by the Children's Hospital at Westmead, Sydney, Australia over a period of 10 years.

- 1) We achieve our goal using the Deep Learning algorithm, which is known to analyze non-linear and complex information, such as cell-interactions, effectively.
- 2) We conduct this experiment using the Big Data software called H2O, using R.
- 3) We first experimented with the standard Deep Learning parameters, and later adjusted the size and shape of the general network by optimizing the depth and retention factor of hidden neurons.
- 4) We improved the accuracy by using the techniques of Out-of-Bag Sampling, Bagging and Voting.

We later tuned H2O's platform-specific network parameters.

- 5) Later, the number of votes needed to obtain the highest accuracy of predictions, is also tuned.
- 6) We built confusion matrices for each of our Deep Learning models to evaluate how well our models perform.

RESULTS:

The Deep Learning technique had to be adapted to the given two datasets and the constraints of H2O to solve the problem of mortality prediction. The parameters and hyper-parameters were adjusted as follows:

- 1) The retention factor of 2/3 and the activation function of Tanh were used for both the datasets.
- 2) The input dropout ratio and the number of epochs was 0.1 and 80 respectively for SNP whereas it was 0.01 and 400 respectively for the Affy dataset.
- 3) The 16-layer deep model for SNP had the configuration (3000, 2000, 1320, 870, 575, 380, 250, 165, 100, 66, 40, 25, 17, 11, 7, 3). On the other hand, the 17-layer deep model for Affy had the configuration (4000, 2640, 1740, 1140, 750, 495, 325, 210, 138, 90, 60, 40, 25, 16, 10, 7, 3).
- 4) We obtained samples using the technique of Out-of-Bag sampling and used 17 and 15 votes to determine the final predicted outcome of patients in the SNP and Affy datasets respectively.

To assess how well our Deep Learning models perform, we used the measures of accuracy, sensitivity and specificity and compared it with physicians' predictions.

- 1) The physician's predictions for the SNP dataset had an accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of 86%, 72% and 88% respectively compared to our scores of 100% each, after voting.
- 2) The physician's predictions for the Affymetrix dataset had an accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of 86%, 65% and 90% respectively compared to our scores of 98%, 87% and 100% respectively, after voting.

CONCLUSIONS:

Our results are promising as they are corroborated by the clinical dataset and they perform better than the physicians' predictions.

KEYWORDS:

Deep Learning; Leukemia; mortality

BIOGRAPHY:

Reena Shaw is a lover of all things data, spicy food and Alfred Hitchcock. She recently graduated with a Master's in Computer Science from Queen's University with her Thesis in Deep Learning, and resides in Toronto. [She is an organizing member](#) of the Toronto Machine Learning Summit. She is also an [immensely popular author](#) of Data Science and Machine Learning articles for KDnuggets.

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